
SWOT Analysis Of E - Learning Impact On Academic Libraries

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.17270876

Abstract:

In today's era of information and technology, e-learning has gained great importance due to the radical changes in the field of education. Through e-learning, we can learn at our convenience. The impact of these changes is also visible on academic libraries. Due to e-learning, the nature of libraries has changed from traditional to digital. SWOT analysis technique provides an important direction for determining library goals, strategies and development. It can be linked to global knowledge. Although the opportunities for acquiring knowledge have increased, some threats cannot be avoided. By adapting to changing technologies, the challenges facing the role of traditional libraries cannot be ignored. Therefore, libraries need to provide safe, reliable and quality services with the help of proper planning, collaboration, and technical skills, academic libraries can become knowledge-rich digital centers if a balanced integration of e-learning and libraries is achieved.

Keyword: *E-learning, Digital Library, SWOT, Aspects of E-learning, Online education, Digital Transformation, Education Technology.*

Introduction:

In today's era of information and technology, there have been radical changes in the field of education. Along with traditional classroom education, e-learning i.e. online education is gaining priority. With the help of internet, computers, smartphones and various digital tools, acquiring knowledge has become easier and faster which is saving valuable time and money of the users. E-education includes not only study and teaching but also educational administration, policy, management and evaluation. We can study at our convenience through virtual classrooms, virtual universities as well as open educational resources.

“E-learning is a method of education based on formal teaching but with the help of

electronic resources.” The transfer of human skills and knowledge takes place through e-learning. E-learning is being widely accepted due to the advancement in technology and changes in the education system.

These changes are also reflected in academic libraries. The use of e-resources for organizing, storing, preserving, disseminating and retrieving information has increased. Previously limited to printed books, libraries are now providing e-books, e-journals, databases, digital repositories and online services. This has enabled students and teachers to access the necessary information from anywhere and at any time. E-learning has transformed the nature of libraries from traditional to modern and they are becoming digital centers of knowledge. Due to

digitalization, libraries are prioritizing the provision of e-services and e-resources to their readers. The impact of e-learning has brought about a radical change in library services and management. Effective management techniques must be implemented to lead any organization or business on the path of progress. The library is considered the centerpiece of any educational institution and it is also a growing institution.

Planning is an important factor in management. To understand the impact of e-learning on a library, planning through SWOT analysis techniques can identify the library's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. The concept of SWOT is formed from an acronym of four elements: Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats. Using this technique in library planning provides important direction in determining and developing library goals and strategies.

Literature Review:

Khan, Javed (2016) E-learning is an evolving field that evolves with time and research. E-learning has revolutionized the education sector and facilitated the delivery of education. E-learning has also changed library services and information services. This article discusses the need for e-learning, advantages of e-learning, disadvantages and impact of e-learning on library services.

Widiaty, Wahyudin and Abdullah (2019) this paper aims to review and analyze the impact of digital library systems on users. Digital library can control plagiarism, create learning materials without sifting through numerous books; students can easily acquire knowledge through digital materials, easy access to users. Disadvantages include lack of copyright rights; e-documents have to go through multiple stages, technical difficulties like data loss, lights off etc.

Lihitkar, Naidu and Lihitkar (2013) this paper discusses e-learning programs and initiatives and challenges in library and information science in India. The study finds that 23 universities are running e-learning programs for library and informatics at undergraduate, postgraduate, and certificate levels. Some universities run short-term courses for LIS education. Most universities use Moodle software for e learning program. This study will help students and LIS professionals to design e-learning models for their department. Students will learn e-learning courses provided by a particular institute. Institutions that have not yet developed an e-learning curriculum will benefit from this paper to understand e-learning courses in LIS education.

Objective:

1. To study the strengths of E-learning on Academic libraries.
2. To study the weakness of E-learning on Academic libraries.
3. To study the Opportunities of E-learning on Academic libraries.
4. To study the Threats of E-learning on Academic libraries.

E-Learning:

E-learning is an electronic form of education such as web-based learning, computer-based learning and virtual classroom. It involves the delivery of content through the Internet, LAN/WAN, audio and video tapes, satellite, broadcasting or CD-ROM etc. The system in which education is based on formal education and is taken with the help of e-resources is called e-learning. E-learning is a broad and far-reaching concept that adopts educational technology through electronics. This concept of e-learning adopts distance learning methods instead of

traditional teaching methods. E-learning has been developed to implement information technology applications in education. E-learning is also known as virtual learning, internet-based training, web-based training, digital educational collaboration etc. Web blogs, social bookmarking, internet telephony, Wikipedia, RSS (Really Simple Syndication), podcasting, instant messaging, text chat, video conferencing are e-learning tools. In e-learning, the instructor and the student are separated by space or time, and the distance between the student and the instructor is reduced through the use of online technological tools. To strengthen distance learning, many universities are developing e-learning courses. In this, many experts come together to deliver lectures on different topics and try to reach the users with the help of technology.

Need of E Learning:

E-learning has become an essential aspect of modern education. In this, students can access courses and materials anytime, anywhere. Therefore, students in rural areas can also study easily. E-learning bridges the gap in education in rural and remote areas. This education encourages self-learning. Students can adapt to different learning styles and schedules and progress at their own pace. E-learning also saves on the cost of education, as there is no need for travel, accommodation and printed materials. The use of multimedia makes education more engaging and promotes digital literacy and skills. Institutions can provide learning opportunities to thousands of students through a single platform. Therefore, e-learning has become a necessity in today's digital age.

E - Learning Impact on Academic Libraries:

Strengths:

Easy Availability of Resources:

There are no physical boundaries to access education resources through E-learning. E-learning enables students and teachers to use e-books, e-journals, databases, along with syllabus, question papers, company data, government or private surveys, historical and geographical documents, other subject's resources for research. The access can in the campus or remote access from anywhere anytime. Every user can easily access these e-resources on mobile or computer.

Time and Money Saving:

E-learning does not require students to be physically present in a traditional library. Therefore, they can study at their own place. Since students can study from anywhere, this saves time. The databases or e-resources are purchased by college or university and made available to the students. So online resources are usually free for students or staff and users saves their money along with time.

Expansion of Knowledge Resources:

Digital resources are not limited to just one library but can be used worldwide, thus helping in the expansion of knowledge resources. Due to the expansion of knowledge resources, students can easily get information and knowledge about any field. It boosts our intellectual development. It effects in the increasing use of library resources.

Improvement of Teacher-Student Interaction:

E-learning platforms allow teachers and students to interact with each other through digital classroom, virtual classroom, online discussions, forums, e-mail, etc. E-learning keeps user engaged where user have increasing interest in their education and research. E-education keep user in touch of

teacher and library because there is facility to user to interact with them and ask about any query.

Cost and Space Saving:

Some e-resources are available for free. Also, e-books and e-journals are cheaper than printed books. This reduces the financial burden on the library. Printed materials require a lot of space. But digital materials can be stored in large quantities in less space. This also saves space.

Promotes Self-Learning:

Audio, video, e-books, databases, online lectures are made freely and easily available to students, which allows for a variety of learning styles. Students, teachers or researchers can learn anytime and at any age. This encourages lifelong learning and is important for the educational expansion of the library.

Technical Aptitude:

E-learning makes the library more technologically capable. The use of RFID, OPAC, digital repository increases. It helps in learning new concepts in technology and increases our intellectual capabilities. Overall library users are automatically taking interest and becoming techno Savy

Weakness:**Technical Issues:**

Technical issues such as internet speed, network connectivity, power outages, software and hardware failures, and shortage of computers or equipment can cause disruptions in the provision of library services.

Expensive Equipment:

Libraries cannot afford the equipment required to provide e-services such as computer systems, high-speed internet connections, e-books, e-journals, database subscriptions, RFID technology, servers and cloud storage facilities, and virtual classrooms.

Lack of Personal Interaction:

In the traditional education printed books or other physical reading material used since long ago and habit of these resources is still dwells in human being. There is a lack of the experience of sitting in the library and studying, the joy of touching books. Other reading materials available in the library cannot be handled.

Copyright and Access Limitations:

Since many e-books and databases are license-based, not everyone gets full access. This places limitations on the use of many databases.

Distractions in Studies:

While studying online, students can get distracted by social media, games, advertisements. Also, in e-learning, since the teacher is not physically present, he cannot focus on all the students. Due to this, there is a lack of concentration among the students.

Lack of Technical Skills:

Many users find it difficult to use computers and e-learning tools properly. This can lead to gaps in learning. Lack of technical skills makes it difficult to verify the authenticity of information available online. Choosing reliable sources becomes a challenge.

Mental and Physical Effects:

Continuous screen time can lead to eye strain, lack of physical activity, and increased feelings of loneliness. There is a lack of communication with others.

Opportunities:**Development of Digital Libraries:**

E-learning provides libraries with the opportunity to develop digital collections by integrating e-books, e-journals, e-thesis and databases. This makes it easier to access, store, search and share information.

Development of best services and Practices:

Librarians get the opportunity to provide e-services like e-reference service, OPAC, current awareness service, remote access and resource sharing, online literature search, digital repository, webinars. E-learning gives libraries the opportunity to use best practices (RFID, OPAC, Institutional Repository, barcode system, cloud storage, mobile apps)

Boosting Research:

E-learning tools and e-resources make it easier for researchers to find up-to-date information and resources, and they can search for more information in less time, thereby increasing the speed and quality of research.

Collaboration and Networking:

Libraries of different educational institutions can come together and exchange books, journals, databases and other information. Students, teachers and other members of the community can also access the reading material they need through any library network in the world. This can encourage their lifelong learning.

Threats:**Cyber Security Threats:**

Infected files pose a risk of data hacking, data theft, deletion or blocking. This can lead to library services being shut down or causing financial losses. Keeping information secure in digital libraries is challenging.

Copyright Infringement:

The risk of unauthorized use of original materials, artwork, music, books, films, software, etc. created by an individual increases. Illegal acts such as free exchange of e-books or e-journals in libraries, unauthorized installation of software in educational institutions can occur.

Decline in Library Usage:

With information readily available in digital form, the tendency to purchase paper copies of books and the demand for physical books has also decreased. This eliminates the need for printing and maintenance costs.

Overload Information:

The vast amount of information available on the internet makes it difficult for students to choose the right and reliable source. There is a risk of uploading incorrect or false information.

Digital Divide:

Students from rural areas or economically backward regions are deprived of education due to a lack of resources. The internet availability is the major concern in the rural area which cause to increase digital divide. Not everyone gets equal opportunity to learn. This risks increasing educational inequality.

Challenge to the traditional role of the library:

Library digitization may reduce the need for the traditional library and threaten the librarianship profession. Digitization may also challenge the traditional role of the library. The traditional tasks of librarians (classification of books, registration, etc.) have now been simplified with the help of software. Therefore, their role will have to be redefined.

Conclusion:

E-learning has brought about a remarkable change in the scope and nature of academic libraries. Information has become easily and quickly accessible to students and teachers. This helps in improving the quality of education and also connects with global knowledge. However, while opportunities for knowledge have increased, there are also some challenges and threats that we cannot avoid. The realities of technological issues, digital

divide, cyber threats, and challenges in the role of traditional libraries cannot be ignored. Therefore, libraries need to adapt to ever-changing technologies and provide safe, reliable, and quality services. The use of SWOT techniques in planning a digital library provides important direction for determining library goals, strategies, and development. With proper planning, collaboration, and technical skills, a balanced integration of e-learning and libraries can be achieved. Academic libraries can become knowledge-rich digital hubs.

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